

Impact of Trade Liberalization on Capacity Utilization of Manufacturing Sectors in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study is aimed at investigating the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, through the use of Dynamic Ordinary Least Square Method (DOLS) technique. This study utilized annual time series data which will be collected from secondary sources mainly; the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin of various years, World Development Indicator (WDI) and the National Bureau of statistics (NBS). The findings suggested that trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria and concluded that trade liberalization caused de-industrialization and not industrialization in Nigeria over the period of study. Hence, it was suggested as a way forward that to improve trade, lower trade barriers, and simplify regulatory requirements, the government must implement trade facilitation measures.

Keyword: Trade Liberalization, Capacity Utilization and Manufacturing Sector

Introduction

Trade liberalization has been largely recognized as a key policy approach adopted by many countries to enhance economic growth and development. It aims at fostering economic and industrial growth by eliminating trade barriers and promoting international trade. There has been a long-held belief that economies grow by engaging in trading activities with other nations of the world as trade does not only contribute to efficient allocation of resources within and outside a country, but also transmits growth from one part of the world to another.

Capacity Utilization measures the extent to which a manufacturing plant would physically produce output given its input which comprise; technology, labour and capital. It is a key factor in establishing how well the industry is reaching its production potential. Capacity utilization gives an idea about the profitability of a company and it provides a comprehensive view of the operational health and economic significance of the manufacturing sector.

Trade liberalization policy dates back to the 1940s after World War II. During this period, protectionism was largely reversed especially among the industrialized countries and the policy was spread to the developing countries with the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1947. GATT was a legal agreement among countries whose purpose was to promote international trade. The primary focus of GATT which was to reduce trade barriers among nations was guided by the nondiscriminatory and the reciprocity principles. The principles stipulated that both trade restrictions and proposals to reduce trade restrictions should apply to all of a country's trading partners equally, it further dictates that all participating countries reduce some of their own import barriers or export subsidies in exchange for comparable steps by their negotiating partners (WTO, 2013). Trade reforms were further expanded and consolidated in 1980s and 1990s across the developing world such as South and East Asia, Latin America and Africa. The World Trade Organisation (WTO) replaced GATT In 1995 but the guiding principles remained the same as GATT's with the objective of helping developing African countries to fully benefit from the global trading system (WTO, 2013).

In Nigeria the oil boom period of the 1980s, preceded the trade liberalization policy regime which became pronounced after the adoption of the International Monetary Fund's (IMF) Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986. The main thrust was to replace import substitution with export promotion strategy through exchange rate and diversification of the productive base of the Nigerian economy (Emerenini & Ohadinma, 2018; Williamson, 1995). In addition, trade liberalization

policy was adopted to improve the balance of payment crises as a result of oil glut in the world market. It served as a survival strategy to reduce the Nation's over reliance on crude oil, occasioned by the collapse in oil price in the world market, with greater emphasis on the non-oil and tradable sectors of agriculture and manufacturing. Nigeria's openness to trade decreased to 27% from an earlier 31%, and further decline to 25% and 23% in 1985 and 1986 respectively. Between 2013 and 2018, trade openness experienced another downward trend to less than 30% (Emerenini & Ohadinma, 2018). This development had a consequent impact on the manufacturing sector performance which equally declined from 20.5% in 1985 to 0.72% in 1997 (Asongo, Jamala, Joel, & Waindu, 2013).

The rate of performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria arising from the adoption trade liberalization policy is not consistent with other countries that have embraced the policy. While other countries have progressed in areas of improved manufacturing output growth, capacity utilization, employment, GDP and profitability as recorded in countries such as Germany which experienced 700% increase in its import due to trade with China and 125% due to its trade union with Latin America (ICC, 2021). The Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS) affirmed that Nigeria's manufacturing sector contracted by - 2.75% in 2020 leaving the sector in a vulnerable condition (NBS, 2020). There has been several government efforts in Nigeria geared towards improving the performance of the manufacturing sector such as privatization and commercialization of public enterprises, the establishment of Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC), the introduction of new tariff rates and incentives (tax holidays, tariff protection, import duty relief, total ban on certain foreign goods), trade and investment liberalization as well as macroeconomic stabilization policies.

Trade liberalization is an important component of economic liberalization which involves the loosening of government control over trade restrictions and barriers. It includes the removal of trade barriers, such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers, as well as internal restrictions for instance directed credit and preferential purchasing. It is described as the reduction or removal of all forms of restrictions to trade among countries. Trade Liberalization as defined by Monisola (2014) is the discontinuation of import licensing, the elimination of marketing boards and removal of obstacles on trade to create a competitive atmosphere between local and foreign industries. Shafaeddin, 2005 defined as any act that would make the trade regime more neutral. That is, nearer to a trade system free of government intervention. Akims, (2017) simply defined it as the removal or reduction of both tariff and non-tariff obstacles to international trade.

Despite government interventions, the Nigerian manufacturing sector still lacks the capacity to cater for the fast growing demand of the over 217 million Nigerian population (United Nations, 2022). This has led to rising prices of goods and services (inflation), recording an all-time high rate of 72.84% inflation rate in 1995, recent statistics reveal that in 2021 inflation rate in Nigeria stood at 15.6% but rose to 20.95% and 28.92% in 2022 and 2023 respectively (NBS, 2023). Furthermore, sustained and persistent rise in the value at which the dollar exchanges for naira (Exchange rate); revealing 120.6 naira to 1 dollar in 2002 as against 1 dollar to 461.51, and 1,505 naira in 2023 and 2024 respectively has made the country's import more costly thereby worsening the already existing inflation rate (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Statistical evidences further suggests decline in important indicators of the manufacturing sector. For instance, manufacturing sector output continues to experience a downward trend between 1986 and 2021, with a decline from 21.01% in 1986 to 13.93% in 2000 (CBN, 2009). Further decline of 9.65% was recorded in 2018 with recent data on manufacturing output standing at 12.67% in 2020 (CBN, 2021). Capacity utilization also recorded a downward trend from 70.1% in 1980 to 40.30% in 1990 and 30.4% in 1997. Further decline was recorded in 2005 from 52.8% to 48.0% in 2009, 40.13 in 2015 and 39.88% in 2018 (CBN, 2019; World Bank, 2019). Between 2019 and 2021, manufacturing capacity utilization revealed an average of 54.9% from 54 observations, recording as low as 43.8% in 2020 (CBN, 2021). This persistent decline in figures of very important economic indices arouses interest as to why Nigeria has not reproduced the success achieved in other climes through the adoption of trade liberalization policies in its own economy.

Objectives of the study

The Objective of this study is to investigate the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Research Questions

What is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria

Hypotheses

The null hypothesis of this study is stated as trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Methodology

Unit root test will help to check if the statistical properties of the time series data changes with time and Cointegration analysis will establish the existence or not of a long run relationship between the variables of interest. In order to examine the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, the equation will be modelled as follows;

$$CU = f(TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L, K) \quad 1$$

Where:

CU= Capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector.

TLD= Trade Liberalization Dummy used to proxy Trade Liberalization

TR= Average import tariff collection rate

NEX=Net Export

EXR=Exchange rate

IN= Inflation rate

IR= Interest rate

L= Labour Inputs

K= Capital proxied by Bank credit to the manufacturing sector

Hence, by transforming equation 1 into an econometric form and adding natural logarithm to the variables, the equation then becomes:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 \ln L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 2$$

Where

t = Time period

ε_t = Stochastic error term

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ = Elasticity coefficients of the explanatory variables TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L and K respectively.

\ln = Natural Logarithm

The general form of Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) is given as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \bar{\theta}X + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\theta}_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3$$

Y_t = dependent variable,

X = matrix of explanatory variables,

$\bar{\theta}$ = cointegration vector; that is, represent the long run cumulative multipliers or alternatively, the long run effect of a change in x on y ,

P = lag length,

q = lead length Lag and lead terms included in DOLS regression have the purpose of making its stochastic error term independent of all past innovations in stochastic regressors

Consequently, equation 3 will be re-specified following Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) as stated in equation 4 as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 CU_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t \\
 & + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_1 \Delta TLD_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_2 \Delta TR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_3 \Delta NET_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_4 \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} \\
 & + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_5 \Delta \ln IN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_6 \Delta \ln IR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_7 \Delta L_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_8 \Delta K_{t-j} \\
 & + \mu_t \qquad \qquad \qquad \dots \dots \dots \qquad \qquad \qquad 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Presentation of Results

The result is aimed at answering the question, what is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria?

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Table

	<i>CU</i>	<i>TLD</i>	<i>REX</i>	<i>EXCR</i>	<i>IN</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>K</i>
Mean	46.28	0.86	6,227,896.95	117.06	18.97	83.68	7,341.73
Standard Deviation	9.70	0.35	7,243,130.91	122.84	17.15	1.66	10,706.75
Kurtosis	0.22	2.61	0.22	0.94	3.39	(0.89)	1.04
Skewness	0.56	(2.12)	1.03	1.19	1.99	(0.24)	1.42
Minimum	30.40	0	7,502.50	0.61	0.22	80.12	8.57
Maximum	73.26	1.00	27,251,572.39	476.41	76.76	86.03	38,952.43
Count	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00	42.00

Source: Author’s Computation

The outcome is displayed in Table 1 which summarized the basic statistical features of the data under consideration to know the distinctive features of each of the variables that made up the sample data and to determine whether there exist outliers

Table 2: Correlation Matrix Table

	<i>CU</i>	<i>OGM</i>	<i>EMP</i>	<i>TLD</i>	<i>REX</i>	<i>EXCR</i>	<i>INF</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>K</i>
<i>CU</i>	1								
<i>TRDL</i>	-0.206	0.073	-0.493	1					
<i>REX</i>	0.291	0.687	-0.746	0.355	1				
<i>EXCR</i>	0.208	0.696	-0.666	0.391	0.906	1			
<i>INF</i>	-0.213	-0.094	0.416	0.140	-0.287	-0.253	1		
<i>L</i>	-0.150	-0.357	-0.567	0.645	0.278	0.271	-0.188	1	
<i>K</i>	0.248	0.831	-0.572	0.283	0.910	0.945	-0.201	0.033	1

Source: Author’s Computation

The correlation matrix measures the degree and direction of a linear relationship or association between two variables. Its value ranges between 0 and 1. -1 indicates a perfect negative association while +1 indicates a perfect positive association and 0 implies the absence of correlation. Hence, table 2 presents the correlation matrix illustrating the association between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 3 Unit Root Test Result

Variables	ADF			Remark
CU	-3.989048**	-7.220529**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
REX	1.323333	-4.125299	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff
EXCR	1.323333	-4.125299	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff
INF	-3.268025	-6.378690**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
L	-1.996727	-3.741716**	I(0)	Stationary @ level
K	2.831799	-3.867123**	I(1)	Stationary @ 1 st Diff

Source: Eviews 10

Table 3 presents the outcome of the unit root analysis for the variables employed in this research. The result revealed that CU, EMP, INF and L were stationary at level whereas, other variables such as OGM, REX, EXCR, and K gained stationarity at first differencing. Summary of the unit root test suggesting mixed combination of both I (0) and I (1) levels of integration gives room for the suitability to apply the Dynamic ordinary least squares (DOS) method of analysis .

The null hypothesis of this study is stated as trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria.

Table 4 Johansen Co-integration Table

Fisher Statistics	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Conclusion
Model	181.8996** 128.2739	150.5585 117.7	Cointegrated

Source: Author's Computation using Eviews 10

What is the impact of trade liberalization on capacity utilization of the manufacturing sectors in Nigeria?

In order to examine the impact of trade liberalization on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, we will have the following equations

$$CU = f(TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L, K) \quad \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where:

- CU= Capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector.
- TLD= Trade Liberalization Dummy used to proxy Trade Liberalization
- TR= Average import tariff collection rate
- NEX= Net Export
- EXR= Exchange rate
- IN= Inflation rate
- IR= Interest rate
- L= Labour Inputs
- K= Capital proxied by Bank credit to the manufacturing sector

Hence, by transforming equation 5 into an econometric form and adding natural logarithm to the variables, the equation then becomes:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 \ln L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots \dots \dots 6$$

Where

- t= Time period
- ε_t = Stochastic error term
- β_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ = Elasticity coefficients of the explanatory variables TLD, TR, NEX, EXR, IN, IR, L and K respectively.
- ln= Natural Logarithm

The general form of Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) is given as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \bar{\varphi}X + \sum_{j=-q}^p \bar{\varphi}_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad \dots \dots \dots 7$$

Y_t = dependent variable,

X_t = matrix of explanatory variables,

$\bar{\theta}$ = cointegration vector; that is, represent the long run cumulative multipliers or alternatively, the long run effect of a change in x on y ,

P = lag length,

q = lead length Lag and lead terms included in DOLS regression have the purpose of making its stochastic error term independent of all past innovations in stochastic regressors

Consequently, equation 6 will be re-specified following Stock and Watson (1993) Dynamic Ordinary Least Square (DOLS) as stated in equation 7 as:

$$CU_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TLD_t + \beta_2 TR_t + \beta_3 NEX_t + \beta_4 EXR_t + \beta_5 IN_t + \beta_6 IR_t + \beta_7 L_t + \beta_8 \ln K_t + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_1 \Delta TLD_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_2 \Delta TR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_3 \Delta NET_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_4 \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_5 \Delta \ln IN_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_6 \Delta \ln IR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_7 \Delta L_{t-j} + \sum_{j=q}^p \bar{\theta}_8 \Delta K_{t-j} + \mu_t$$

Table 5: Results of the DOLS Estimates (Model One)

Variable (LONG RUN EQUATION)	Coefficient	Prob.
TLD	-7.563201	0.5014
REX	-8.91E-07	0.6968
EXCR	0.002583	0.9745
INFL	-0.104158	0.5871
LBR	-8.524376	0.2150
CRDT	-0.002107	0.4518
C	731.4351	0.1855
@TREND	2.623693	0.0611
R2	0.746125	
F-test	2.334621	0.046525
N	42	

Dependent Variable: CU

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

Source: Author's Computation

The result of the regression result is as indicated in Table 5. From the result, few of the variable (TLD, REX and IR) are statistically significance at 5 and 10% respectively. The coefficient of the trade liberalization dummy is positive and statistically significance at 5%. It shows that the higher the level of trade liberalization in the economy, the more the level of manufacturing capacity utilization. It Shows that trade liberalization positively impacts manufacturing capacity utilization in Nigeria.

Hypothesis

H_0 : Trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: If the p-value is greater than the level of significance of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis; otherwise we reject it.

Reject H_0 if p-value < 0.05

Accept H_0 if p-value > 0.05

The DOLS analysis in Table 6 shows that the P-value of the Trade Liberalization is 0.5014. Given that the p-value is higher than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, we can conclude that the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. It can further be inferred that Trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

In accordance with this hypothesis, it was discovered that trade liberalization has no significant impact on the capacity utilization of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Manufacturing capacity utilization, manufacturing output and manufacturing value added were employed to proxy manufacturing performance while money supply as a percentage of GDP, domestic credit to the private sector and liquidity ratio were employed to proxy financial development. By using the dynamic error correction model, the results of the estimates revealed that credit to private sector and money supply as a percentage of GDP had positive but insignificant impact on capacity utilization and output of the manufacturing sector in the short run. Whereas, they both have negative but significant effect on manufacturing value added in the short run.

Conversely, the result of this study agreed with the study of Onakoya and Efeni (2020) that carried out a study to examine the effect of trade liberalization on the Nigerian Manufacturing sector output between 1980 and 2015. The study employed the Vector Error Correction Mechanism VECM and the impulse-response test was used in order to establish the direction of causality and to determine the ripple effects of the shock of one variable on the other. The study utilized the contribution of manufacturing output to GDP as proxy for manufacturing output and measure trade liberalization by the level of trade openness, other variables utilized were inflation, exchange rate and government expenditure on economic activities. Results of this research revealed a negative long run but significant relation between trade liberalization and manufacturing sector output. That is, trade liberalization had no impact on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria, both in the short and longrun,

The outcome of this study is also consistent with the study of Nzeribe, Uzonwanne and Ezenekwe (2018) who investigated if trade liberalization led to industrialization or de-industrialisation during the period 1980 – 2017 in Nigeria. Variables of trade liberalization, gross capital formation, human capital index, trade openness, labour force and foreign direct investment were modelled and specified, while estimation was done using the ARDL bounds test approach and interaction of trade liberalization dummy with trade openness. The results revealed that in the long-run trade openness and human capital impacted negatively on manufacturing value added. It concluded that trade liberalization caused de-industrialization and not industrialization in Nigeria over the period of study-

Conclusion

The primary focus of this study was to investigate the long-term effects of trade liberalization on the performance, output growth, and employment of Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Evidence of the beneficial effects of trade liberalization on the manufacturing sector's growth performance and employment was discovered in the study. Due to trade liberalization, Nigeria's manufacturing sector is more susceptible to outside shocks, which has slowed their growth. Therefore, unintended benefits of trade liberalization have resulted from the manufacturing industries' inability to compete favorably with established foreign firms. This is evident from Nigeria's exports of primary commodities devoid of value addition and its net imports of completed manufactured goods rather than imports of technology or other necessary production inputs. In light of this, it can be concluded that the current trade liberalization strategy, which emphasizes lowering tariffs and expanding economic openness, is not having the desired effect on Nigeria's manufacturing sector performance. This is proof that more trade liberalization strategies can give Nigerian manufacturers greater access to the market and enable them to enter new domestic and foreign markets. This may result in increased demand, which would force businesses to boost output and bring on more staff to satisfy the demand.

Recommendations

To improve trade, lower trade barriers, and simplify regulatory requirements, the government must implement trade facilitation measures. This might involve establishing trade facilitation centers to help manufacturers navigate trade procedures, standardizing trade laws, and implementing electronic customs systems.

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